

Prediction of cure-induced wrinkles aimed at the manufacturing of large wind turbine blades

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Abstract

This work uses predictive modelling to study the phenomenon of cure-induced wrinkles based on validated experimental model behaviour. The mechanisms that govern the occurrence are studied with emphasis on the need for thermal gradients, causing a variation in thermal expansion and build-up of stiffness across a large monolithic composite laminate to create cure-induced wrinkles. The appearance of wrinkles was evaluated based on the undulated region's maximum amplitude, angle, and wavelength. The angle is especially important for understanding the structural behaviour of the composite material after curing. Boundary conditions were found to affect the wrinkle amplitude and angle. Especially, constraining the laminate against expansion was found to increase the rate at which a wrinkle appears. The pre-cure temperature was found to be the most important parameter to control, as the predictions show that slight variations in the pre-cure temperature greatly influence the angle of the undulated fibres in the laminate. This shows the need for accurate temperature control and the need for uniform temperature across the mould to mitigate wrinkles in the curing process.

Keywords: Wrinkles, Curing, Manufacturing, Defects, Epoxy, Finite element

1. Introduction

In the manufacturing of wind turbine blades, wrinkles are known to occur due to the complexity of the blade geometry and manufacturing process [1–4]. The effect of these wrinkles on the structural performance of the blades can be severe. Especially the compressive performance of the composite part can be significantly impacted, as the out-of-plane fibre-waviness reduces the local compressive stiffness [5] and strength [2–4]. Furthermore, it has also been shown that the fatigue performance is significantly reduced with the increasing magnitude of the wrinkle [2]. Most previous studies looking into the performance impact of wrinkles have been based on artificially generated wrinkles and thus were not directly coupled with realistic manufacturing-induced wrinkles [2–4]. Besides a study by Broberg et al. [1], there is a need for studies on how wrinkles appear in the manufacturing process of wind turbine blades. Studies of the liquid moulding process and curing effects on the formation of wrinkles have yet to be investigated.

The lack of manufacturing centric studies means that the exact reasons for any specific wrinkle are not always easily determined. Several studies have looked into the drapability of the fabrics as a governing

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factor [6, 7], where the shearing, compression, and bending of the fabrics were analysed as mechanisms for driving the onset of wrinkles. This work investigates a specific scenario for wrinkling driven by thermal gradients during the curing process. Thermal gradients can lead to certain regions curing faster than others, and this uneven curing can lead to a variation in the rate of development of mechanical properties. When combined with the thermal gradients and hence differences in expansion, it is possible for the more cured region to push on the lesser cured region, resulting in undulated fibres.

A possible manufacturing scenario where this specific mechanism can result in the formation of wrinkles is shown in Figure 1. This represents a simplified version of a large wind turbine blade mould consisting of several sub-sectional moulds which leads to gaps between heated regions. Marked with a dotted box, a region of interest across two mould cross-sections is selected. At this region of interest, the mould consists of two heating elements joined together by a junction. The junction is an extension to the heating elements to allow for the joining of the mould sections. This is considered a critical region where the junction will create a gap between the heating elements and, thus, a delayed heating of the laminate directly above the junction, marked with dotted lines in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The Principle of a laminate placed in a large turbine blade mould and the cross-section in YZ-plane at a region of interest placed across a junction in the turbine blade mould.

This work explores the behaviour and mechanisms triggering the wrinkles for this scenario and studies the parameters controlling the magnitude of cure-induced wrinkles and the possible ways of mitigating them. SOME CLOSING STATEMENT ON OTHER MECHANISMS INCLUDING ANY APPROPRIATE CITATIONS

2. Theory

2.1. Heat transfer

This section deals with the properties necessary to capture the temperature changes inside the laminate. The heat transfer simulations will be governed by the principal Fourier heat transfer equation for

conduction

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_y \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) + k_z \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \right) + \dot{Q}''' \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{Q}''' = \rho_m H_T \frac{dX}{dt},$$

where T is the temperature, t is time, and y and z comprise the two dimensions of the cartesian coordinate system over which the problem is solved. The specific heat capacity, c_p , density ρ , and conductivity k_i are the relevant material properties, with the conductivity being directional such that i is either y or z . The function \dot{Q}''' represents the internal heat generation, which is zero for parts other than the resin. In the function for \dot{Q}''' , H_T is the enthalpy of reaction (the exothermal heat released during the cure). The conductivities in (1) are in the global coordinate system but in the local coordinates for the resin and fibres with k_f and k_m with index f denoting the fibre and m the matrix material. Both the resin and fibres are assumed to be isotropic.

The resin density is accounted for in the heat transfer equation and its contribution to the thermal effect in the resin

$$\rho_m = \rho_m^{\text{init}} X + (X_{\text{end}} - X) \rho_m^{\text{end}}, \quad (2)$$

is modelled using the rule of mixture between the resin density of the uncured resin, ρ_m^{init} , and the fully cured resin system, ρ_m^{end} . The densities were measured [8]. The parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Thermal properties of the glass fibres and resin.

k_m [W/(m ² K)]	k_f [W/(m ² K)]	$c_{p,m}$ [J/(kgK)]	$c_{p,f}$ [J/(kgK)]	H_T [J/kg]	ρ_m^{init} [kg/m ³]	ρ_m^{end} [kg/m ³]	ρ_f [kg/m ³]
0.14 [9]	1.3 [10]	1900 [11]	810 [10]	4.7×10^5 [12]	1088	1145	2600

2.2. Cure kinetic model and Glass transition temperature

The resin properties are based on the behaviour of the epoxy resin investigated in [8, 12]. A cure kinetic model [13] is defined as

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = \frac{K(T)X^m(1-X)^n}{1 + \exp[C(X - X_c(T))]}, \quad (3)$$

$$K(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{e_a}{RT}\right),$$

$$X_c(T) = X_{cT}T + X_{c0}.$$

The cure kinetic model incorporates in the nominator the Arrhenius reaction equation, $K(T)$, which consists of the pre-exponential factor, A , the activation energy, e_a , the universal gas constant, R and the power law coefficients n and m . In the denominator, the model is described by an exponential function which captures the reduction in the rate of cure, dX/dt , caused by the reduced molecular mobility at higher degrees of cure through the critical degree of cure, X_c . The X_c is computed using the baseline critical degree of cure, X_{c0} , and the increase in the critical degree of cure per increase in unit temperature, X_{cT} . Finally,

the diffusion constant, C , describes how abrupt the change in reaction rate is. The critical degree of cure depends on the glass transition temperature, T_g . The DiBenedetto relation [14]

$$T_g(X) = T_{g0} + \frac{\xi X(T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})}{1 - (1 - \xi)X}. \quad (4)$$

relates X to the midpoint value of the glass transition temperature, T_g . The relation involves the final T_g for a state of complete cure, $T_{g\infty}$, the initial T_g for a state of zero cure, T_{g0} , and a fitting parameter, ξ . The latter represents the ratio of the segmental mobility of the fully cured polymer to that of the initial monomers under the assumption of constant lattice energies [15].

The degree of cure X , is calculated through numerical integration

$$X = \int_0^t \frac{dX}{dt} dt. \quad (5)$$

The integrated X depend on temperature T and time t , relating the cure kinetic model in (3) to the specific cure profile applied to the studied epoxy resin. The model parameters for (3)-(4) have been determined for a wind turbine blade grade epoxy resin [12] and are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters used for the prediction of X and T_g of the specific resin system [12].

A [s ⁻¹]	e_a [kJ/mol]	n [-]	m [-]	C [-]	X_{cT} [K ⁻¹]	X_{c0} [-]	T_{g0} [°C]	ξ [-]	$T_{g\infty}$ [°C]
$2.50 \cdot 10^5$	56.24	1.83	0.41	43.7	$5.27 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-0.885	-42.0	0.487	89.0

2.3. Incremental strain contribution

The total strain increment of the fibre and matrix system can be split up into

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\varepsilon_m^{\text{tot}} &= \Delta\varepsilon_m^{\text{mech}} + \Delta\varepsilon_m^{\text{th}} + \Delta\varepsilon_m^{\text{ch}}, \\ \Delta\varepsilon_f^{\text{tot}} &= \Delta\varepsilon_f^{\text{mech}} + \Delta\varepsilon_f^{\text{th}}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2.3.1. Thermal strain

The thermal strain, $\Delta\varepsilon^{\text{th}}$, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\varepsilon_m^{\text{th}} &= \alpha_m \Delta T, \\ \Delta\varepsilon_f^{\text{th}} &= \alpha_f \Delta T. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Several studies [8, 16–18] have shown that the resin thermal expansion can be rather complex in its relationship to temperature and degree of cure. The model proposed by Jørgensen et al. [8] will be used in this work. As this work only aims to investigate the load-transferring part of the thermal expansion, the model sets the expansion coefficient of the resin before X_σ to zero

$$\alpha_m^{\text{h}} = \alpha_m^{\text{c}} = 0, \quad X < X_\sigma. \quad (8)$$

In [8], it was experimentally found to be important to distinguish between heat-up α_m^h and cool-down α_m^c . The thermal expansion for heating-up was found to evolve like

$$\alpha_m^h = \begin{cases} \alpha_g, & T^* < T'_1 \\ a_1(T^* - T'_1) + \alpha_g, & T'_1 \leq T^* < T'_2 \\ a_2(T^* - T'_2) + a_1(T'_2 - T'_1) + \alpha_g, & T'_2 \leq T^* < T'_3 \\ a_3^h(T^* - T'_3) + a_2(T'_3 - T'_2) + a_1(T'_2 - T'_1) + \alpha_g, & T'_3 \leq T^* < T'_4 \\ a_4^h(T^* - T'_4) + a_3^h(T'_4 - T'_3) + a_2(T'_3 - T'_2) + a_1(T'_2 - T'_1) + \alpha_g, & T'_4 \leq T^* < T'_5 \\ \alpha_{Xm}, & T^* \geq T'_5 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where T^* is the difference between the instantaneous and glass transition temperatures (i.e. $T - T_g$). Below the glass transition temperature, $T^* < T'_1$, the thermal expansion was found to be constant, α_g , followed by an increase of the thermal expansion coefficient, here described by the parameters a_1 , a_2 , a_3^h and a_4^h as the temperature approaches and crosses T_g through the parameters T'_2 to T'_5 .

Similar to the heat-up, the cooldown is described by α_r^c as

$$\alpha_m^c = \begin{cases} \alpha_g, & T^* < T'_1 \\ a_1(T^* - T'_1) + \alpha_g, & T'_1 \leq T^* < T'_2 \\ a_2(T^* - T'_2) + a_1(T'_2 - T'_1) + \alpha_g, & T'_2 \leq T^* < T'_4 \\ \alpha_{Xm}, & T^* \geq T'_4 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The heat-up and cooldown-dependent thermal expansion parameters are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameters [8] fitted for the thermal expansion model (9) and (10) based on FBG measurements of reheated cured specimen.

α_g [K ⁻¹]	a_1 [K ⁻²]	a_2 [K ⁻²]	a_3^h [K ⁻²]	a_4^h [K ⁻²]
7.11×10^{-5}	6.85×10^{-7}	2.67×10^{-6}	1.08×10^{-5}	-9.19×10^{-6}
T'_1 [K]	T'_2 [K]	T'_3 [K]	T'_4 [K]	T'_5 [K]
-50	-22	-11	-3	2.5

Above the glass transition temperature, the thermal expansion increases with X for α_m^h and α_m^c . The cure-dependent thermal expansion is found to be fitted quite well by a second-order polynomial

$$\alpha_{Xm} = a_{X2}X^2 + a_{X1}X + a_{X0}. \quad (11)$$

with the fitting parameters a_{X2} , a_{X1} and a_{X0} . The fitted parameters are given in Table 4.

Table 4: The fitted parameters [8] for the function α_{Xm} (11). This relation is only valid for values of $X > X_\sigma$.

a_{X0} [K ⁻¹]	a_{X1} [K ⁻¹]	a_{X2} [K ⁻¹]
-96.0×10^{-5}	209.6×10^{-5}	-98.1×10^{-5}

2.3.2. Chemical strain

The incremental linear chemical strain for the resin, $\Delta\varepsilon_m^{ch}$, is defined as the incremental isotropic change in the specific volumetric shrinkage following [19] as

$$\Delta\varepsilon_m^{ch} = \sqrt[3]{1 + \Delta V_{sh}} - 1. \quad (12)$$

Here, the incremental volumetric shrinkage, ΔV_{sh} , is defined by the volume change of a cubic element normalised by its original volume and thus is unitless. The volumetric shrinkage model is

$$V_{sh} = \begin{cases} 0, & X < X_\sigma \\ V_{sh}^{end} \left(\frac{X - X_\sigma}{X_{end} - X_\sigma} \right)^2, & X_\sigma \leq X < X_{end} \\ V_{sh}^{end}, & X \geq X_{end} \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

considering only the load-transferring volumetric shrinkage. Thus, the volumetric shrinkage equals zero for $X < X_\sigma$. The load-transferring shrinkage develops from $X_\sigma \leq X$ and the volumetric shrinkage remains unchanged for $X_{end} \leq X$. The shrinkage model is set to follow a second-order model Johnston [20]. The parameters for the volumetric shrinkage model are listed in Table 5 and are based on the findings in [8].

Table 5: Parameters [8] for the Johnston volumetric shrinkage model (13) [20].

X_σ [%]	X_{end} [%]	V_{sh}^{end} [%]
69.7	98.0	-1.1

2.3.3. Cure-dependent stiffness

The stiffness of the fibres and resin is important for building stress during the simulation. The stiffness behaviour is important for the phenomenon of cure-induced wrinkles. The stresses are described as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\sigma_m &= E_m \varepsilon_m^{mech}, \\ \Delta\sigma_f &= E_f \varepsilon_f^{mech}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The resin stiffness, E_m , is assumed to build up only with the degree of cure X [19] as

$$E_m = \begin{cases} E_m^0, & X < X_\sigma \\ E_m^0 (1 - X_m) + X_m E_m^\infty, & X_\sigma \leq X < X_{end} \\ E_m^\infty, & X \geq X_{end} \end{cases}, \quad \text{with} \quad (15)$$

$$X_m = \left(\frac{X - X_\sigma}{X_{end} - X_\sigma} \right).$$

The uncured stiffness of the resin, E_m^0 , is zero for $X < X_\sigma$, as the resin is liquid below X_σ . However, a small value of E_m^0 will be used. This value was determined from the shear storage modulus, G' , measured using a rheometer and the value of G' taken at X_σ , assuming a constant Poisson's ratio of the resin is

constant during the simulations [19]. The cured resin stiffness, E_m^∞ , was determined according to ISO527-5 [21] from test coupons obtained from fully cured resin plates. The mechanical properties of the epoxy resin and the glass fibres are compiled in Table 6.

For modelling the glass fibre fabric behaviour, it is necessary to account for the fibre fabric stiffness being lower when the fibre fabric is in compression, and the resin is uncured when $X < X_\sigma$ [7, 22]. The build-up of fibre stiffness in compression is set to follow

$$E_{f,c}(X) = \left(0.01 + \frac{0.99}{1 + \exp(q(X - X_\sigma))} \right) E_f, \quad \varepsilon_f^{mech} < 0. \quad (16)$$

Here, E_f is the tensile Young's modulus of the fibres, and q is a parameter that governs how steep the compressive stiffness builds up once X_σ is reached. The transition is slow for small values of q , and the transition becomes steeper for higher values. The properties used in (16) are compiled into Table 6.

Table 6: Mechanical properties of the epoxy resin and glass fibres used for the simulations.

E_m^0 [MPa]	E_m^∞ [MPa]	ν_m [-]	q [-]	E_f [MPa]	ν_f [-]
0.3	3000	0.4[19]	-10	70×10^3 [10]	0.2[10]

3. Model setup

The model is implemented in the commercial finite element code Abaqus[®], using the user subroutines. UMATHT was used to introduce the heat transfer behaviour in Section 2.1, UEXPAN for the thermal and cure shrinkage expansion behaviour, and a UMAT for the mechanical behaviour in Section 2.3. The whole subroutine is available as a Software Impact paper [23] The model's geometry is illustrated in Figure 2. The model consists of a glass bed (mould) on which the laminate is placed with a thickness, $t_{bed} = 40$ mm. In turbine blade manufacturing, the mould often consists of more durable materials. However, the scenario here uses glass to simplify mould properties and make it possible to conduct laboratory investigations. The glass bed material is taken to have the same properties as the glass fibre material. The laminate is a unidirectional (UD) glass fibre-based composite with the fibre direction in the Z-direction. The epoxy resin and fibre fabric are modelled with a segmented approach as illustrated in Figure 2. The laminate has a thickness $t_{lam} = 50$ mm. The overall FVF was set to 53% as a reasonable fibre volume fraction.

The individual resin and fibre fabric layers have a thickness adjusted to satisfy the FVF determined. Adding up to an equal amount of resin and fibre layers. Therefore, the fifty fibre fabric layers must be 0.53 mm and the fifty resin layers 0.47 mm thick. The fibre fabrics and resin layers are straight along the length of the laminate, L in Figure 2. Until the last 50 mm close to the symmetry region. In this region, the fibres and resin have a slight positive imperfection equal to 0.5 mm in the Y-direction at the symmetry line for all the fibre layers.

The boundary conditions applied can be classified into the letter annotation in Figure 2 as:

A: $h = 0.3 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, $T_{room} = 21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

B: $h = 10 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, $T_{room} = 21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

C: $u_y = 0, h = \infty, T = T(t)$.

D: $u_y = 0, h = 10 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}, T_{room} = 21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

E: $u_z = 0, h = 0 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (symmetry of heat flow).

Figure 2: The model setup was built to simulate cure-induced wrinkle development. The surfaces A, B, C, D and E denote the boundary conditions, and the red stripy line on top denotes the path along which post-processing of the deformation was extracted. The point for evaluating the resin behaviour between the fibres is denoted with a blue dot - $P1$ and a red dot - $P2$.

Where h is the heat transfer coefficient along every boundary. The listed boundary conditions A – E describe the corresponding surface areas in Figure 2. Surface A is the top of the laminate simulated to have thermal insulation on top, having poor convection, h , with the ambient environment of $T = 21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to simulate the presence of a thermal blanket, but otherwise mechanically free. Surface B is a free surface that is mechanically unconstrained and free to have convection with the ambient air. The surface C is mechanically supported underneath, allowing for expansion and contraction of the mould along the Z-direction. The applied temperature $T(t)$ from the heating element is assumed to have a perfect conduction in the interface to the glass bed. The temperature profile $T(t)$ applied combines a pre-cure of 6 hours with $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ followed by a post-cure of 3 hours at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Post-cure is necessary to achieve a fully cured laminate. The whole bottom boundary (surfaces C and D) is simply supported. This narrow region is assumed to have contact with the ambient air. The last face, E, is the symmetry region. Mechanical and thermal behaviours around this boundary are symmetrical. Thermally speaking, this means that the convection through this face is zero, enforcing thermal symmetry. At the top surface of the laminate, a path indicated with a red striped line is placed to evaluate the deformation at the end of the cure at a temperature of $21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

In Figure 3, the meshed model is shown. Only the central part of the last approximately 0.25 m is shown, with the remaining 10 m cropped to focus on the region where the wrinkle will appear. The element type is a plane strain hex element with 8 nodes. The mesh is generated with a constant 1 mm element length along the Z-direction in the 50 mm region with the imperfection. Moving away from this region, the mesh becomes increasingly coarse toward the other end. The magnified regions show the mesh close up in the individual resin and fibre fabric layers. The red region below the laminate is the glass mould.

Figure 3: The model mesh used in the simulations with a crop along the 10-meter symmetrical model.

4. Results

4.1. Behaviour of cure-induced wrinkles

To capture the behaviour of cure-induced wrinkles, a case will be investigated with a length of $L = 20$ m. Figure 4 shows the applied temperature $T(t)$ in the bottom of the figure. The two points evaluated in terms of thermal behaviour are plotted as the blue dot - $P1$ and the red dot - $P2$ according to Figure 2. $P1$ is located at $Z = 0$ and $Y = t_{bed} + t_{lam}/2$, whereas $P2$ is located at $Z = L/2$ and $Y = t_{bed} + t_{lam}/2$. In stage 1., the temperature increase in the laminate is slow due to the mould conductivity and heat capacity. Even though the applied temperature has reached 40°C , the temperature in the laminate is still around room temperature. This results in a degree of cure X being very close to zero in stage 1.. In the next stage 2., after around 4.8 hours, the laminate shows the resin's exothermal effect. Reaching a peak temperature of around 115°C . The predicted temperature peak is found to be rather similar to the experimentally observed peak temperature of 99°C for a 55 mm thick laminate investigated by Lahuerta [24]. During this time, the laminate is curing as shown in Figure 4 but with a big gradient in X . With the highest value being around 75% and the lowest around 25%. At stage 2., it is also observed that the laminate is heavily deformed. Following stage 3. about 1 hour later, the temperature decreases in the laminate towards the end of the applied pre-cure at 40°C . In this short time, the laminate has more or less been cured substantially, surpassing 90% apart from the part closest to the mould, which is still around 50-75% cured. This is where the post-cure becomes relevant, and the temperature increases in the mould to 80°C for 3 hours. After the post-cure, a cooldown follows, and a long dwell at room temperature is required to allow the laminate to settle at this temperature. Stage 4. shows the laminate in a state now surpassing $X > 94\%$. In all the presented simulations, a post-cure ensures that the laminate always fulfils $X > 94\%$ everywhere in the laminate. At the final stage 4. it is observed that the deformation and, i.e. the wrinkle of the laminate is nearly unchanged. Then, the interesting part is the time close to stage 2. where the wrinkle develops.

Figure 5 shows the predictions from 3 to 7 hours of the temperatures and the resin stiffness build-up. Figure 5a shows the simulation with three timestamps indicated with vertical lines; pre-wrinkle at $t = 4.2$ h,

Figure 4: Four relevant stages of curing in the simulation stages. **1.** The beginning of the simulation at $X = 0\%$ and before the temperature is applied in the mould. **2.** The temperature is on a steep exothermal gradient. The gradient of X is high across the region where the wrinkle develops due to the temperature difference. **3.** Just before the post-cure, the temperature drops, but X is still low towards the mould face, and thus, the post-cure is needed. **4.** After the post-cure, the laminate is sufficiently cured, and after cooldown to ambient temperature, the wrinkle remains.

post-wrinkle stage at $t = 5.2$ h. In between, a time-stamp $t = 4.7$ h where the two evaluation points $P1$ and $P2$ are investigated. Observing the temperature difference at this time-stamp in the points $P1$ and $P2$, there is a significant temperature difference of $\Delta T = 29^\circ\text{C}$ in prediction. This temperature difference results in a variation in the degree of cure X and, thus, the build-up of resin stiffness. Figure 5b shows the build-up of resin stiffness in the same time frame as Figure 5a. In the pre-wrinkle timestamp, the stiffness of the resin is the initial value corresponding to the liquid stage of the resin, with $X < X_\sigma$ in any of the two regions. As X_σ is reached in $P2$, the build-up of resin stiffness, as well as thermal expansion of the resin, occurs in this region and is simultaneously capable of transferring loads to the fibres. As for $P1$ $X < X_\sigma$, the resin is much more compliant than $P2$ at the same time. Figure 5b demonstrates this between the pre-wrinkle and post-wrinkle stage, where the two evaluation points, at $t = 4.7$ h shows the difference in resin stiffness between the two regions. This allows for a push on the less cured resin in $P1$, allowing for the buckling of the fibres. It is at this stage that the wrinkle develops.

As the resin stiffness build-up in $P1$ catch up with $P2$ as observed for $t \geq 5.2$ hours in Figure 5b, the post-wrinkle stage has been reached, and the wrinkle has developed. From this point on, the wrinkle has formed, and the only variations observed are due to variations in the thermal expansion.

The deformation of the laminate is evaluated according to the principle illustrated in Figure 6. Here, the displacement out of the plane, u_y , is used to quantify the wrinkle formation along the laminate $Z = 0$ and till the length of the laminate $Z = L$. The nodal values of u_y and Z compute the angle θ and the maximum angle as θ_{max} . The maximum amplitude, δ_{max} , is the absolute sum of the peak-to-valley deformation of u_y as illustrated in Figure 6. Similarly, the half-wavelength, $\lambda/2$, - as the wrinkle is modelled symmetrically -

Figure 5: The temperature and stiffness development in the time frame where the wrinkle appears.

is found as the horizontal distance along Z , between the peak and valley of the wrinkle.

Figure 6: The principal sketch of evaluating the wrinkle deformation in terms of amplitude, δ_{max} , angle, θ_{max} , and half-wavelength, $\lambda/2$.

Figure 7 shows the deformations and angles determined from the path along surface A for the 20-meter laminate. Based on the principle in Section Figure 6, the deformation, $u_z(Z)$, the angle, $\theta(Z)$, along the Z -direction are found. From these, the total amplitude, δ_{max} , the maximum angle, θ_{max} , and the half-wavelength of the wrinkle, $\lambda/2$, is determined for each length L .

For the case of $L = 20$ m, the influence of the imperfection was investigated from a magnitude of 0.1 to 2 mm with a 0.1 mm increase. The final values of θ_{max} , δ_{max} and $\lambda/2$ were found to increase with less than 0.1% by increasing the imperfection in the given interval. In the end, 0.5 mm imperfection was decided as a reasonable imperfection. For the specific case a value of $\delta_{max} = 3.33$ mm and $\theta_{max} = 6.72^\circ$ was found.

4.2. Wrinkle dependency on the laminate length

To evaluate the dependency of the wrinkle on part length, a range of L from 5 to 40 m was investigated. The results, δ_{max} and θ_{max} , are plotted in Figure 8. For shorter laminates, both δ_{max} and θ_{max} are found to be small. However, once the laminate length reaches 10 meters, the size of δ_{max} and especially θ_{max} becomes larger if the laminate becomes longer. Although δ_{max} and θ_{max} grows with longer laminates, θ_{max} becomes larger for longer laminates to a higher degree than δ_{max} . The half-wavelength, $\lambda/2$, was

Figure 7: The deformation u_Z as evaluated along the Z-direction of the laminate from 0 to 0.2 m. The maximum amplitude δ_{max} and θ_{max} are found from the deformation.

found to be around 50 mm for all cases. Demonstrating that the expansion is converted into a larger value of θ_{max} and δ_{max} not influencing $\lambda/2$ for changes to the laminate length.

Figure 8: The maximum amplitude, δ_{max} , and angle, θ_{max} , for the different cases of laminate lengths investigated when the laminate is free. The horizontal black line indicates zero.

4.3. Constraining the elongation

The model is modified in the following so that the laminate is now mechanically constrained against movement in the Z-direction following

$$\text{B: } u_z^B = u_z^E = 0.$$

This is to investigate the possible effects on the expansion and contraction of the laminate when it is constrained. Locking the mechanical boundary at surface B, and thereby setting $u_z = 0$, is a simplification. The boundary acts like a face with infinite stiffness, and such a region's thermal conductivity is not considered. In a real scenario, the constraint could translate into geometrical changes.

The results of this investigation are shown in Figure 9, where the wrinkle amplitude and angle develop similarly to the free. In the constrained cases, however, the behaviour occurs at a much higher rate, as reflected by the lengths investigated from $L = 0.5$ m to 11 m. The study was limited to a $L = 11$ m as above this, the simulation terminated due to divergence. The behaviour due to constraints indicates that if the ends of a laminate are partially or fully constrained, there is a higher likelihood of wrinkles appearing. The half-wavelength of the constrained setup is around 45 mm for all the investigated cases.

Figure 9: The maximum amplitude, δ_{max} , and angle, θ_{max} , for the different cases of laminate lengths investigated when the laminate is constrained. The horizontal black line indicates zero.

4.4. Dependency on the cure profile

Until now, a cure profile of 6 h @ 40 °C + 3h @ 80 °C was used. A series of cure profiles with different pre-cure temperatures, T_{pre} , are investigated in the following. The T_{pre} , investigated range from 30 °C to 50 °C. All the pre-cures are followed by the same post-cure to a substantial cure of $X > 94\%$. The laminate has $L = 20$ m, and the boundary along surface B is free.

Figure 10 show δ_{max} and θ_{max} as function of T_{pre} from 30 °C to 50 °C. A pre-cure at a lower temperature of 30 °C results in no significant wrinkle formation with only the initial $\theta = 0.6^\circ$, due to the imperfection in the laminate. However, a pre-cure temperature above 30 °C is shown to be critical. In terms of $\theta_{T_{pre},max}$ and $\delta_{T_{pre},max}$, increases very significantly for cases up to around $T_{pre} = 34^\circ\text{C}$. For cases above $T_{pre} = 34^\circ\text{C}$ and until a $T_{pre} = 50^\circ\text{C}$, the $\theta_{T_{pre},max}$ and $\delta_{T_{pre},max}$ continues to increase but the angle and amplitude are observed to saturate for these higher pre-cure cases.

Accurate control of the pre-cure temperature is necessary to minimise or mitigate wrinkles altogether, as even the slightest temperature increases critically influence the specific case. As small temperature

Figure 10: The angle and total amplitude for every case with different T_{pre} . The horizontal black line indicates zero.

variations were key to mitigating wrinkles, temperature control concerning temperature difference at the mould is important.

The laminate deformation and the influence of temperature are more clearly shown through Figure 11. The deformation of the laminate pre-cured at $T_{pre} = 30^\circ\text{C}$ shows no signs of deformation apart from the expected cure shrinkage. The following cases show that the angle θ develops through a close relationship between $\lambda/2$ and the amplitude δ . The value of $\lambda/2$ increases for every case investigated, unlike for the investigations related to the length of the laminate. In the temperature investigation δ saturates for $T_{pre} = 40^\circ\text{C}$ and above. For the T_{pre} increases, the general behaviour is that $\lambda/2$ decreases as δ increases, and together, they result in the observed increase in θ .

Figure 11: The deformation from selected cases from the path at surface A. Showing the deformation when the pre-cure temperature changes. The horizontal black line indicates zero.

5. Conclusion

This work has dealt with the behaviour of wrinkles appearing in laminates due to the curing process. The behaviour was investigated in terms of the effects triggering wrinkles. It was found that wrinkles appear due to the thermal behaviour, resulting in variations in the build-up of properties and variations in expansion across the laminate. These effects can be increased or reduced by several important parameters: length, constraints, and, most importantly, the influence of cure temperature during the pre-cure. Controlling the cure temperature to mitigate wrinkles simply by ensuring low-temperature variations in the temperature applied and a uniform temperature across a mould is significant to mitigate wrinkles.

It was found that the wrinkle deformation might not look big in a visual inspection but that the angle might still be high, as the wavelength of the wrinkle was found to decrease with increasingly aggressive cure temperature. The angle of fibre fabrics might, therefore, still be quite high. An important point in the inspection procedure of wrinkle defects.

Four principal stages of a cure-induced wrinkle are shown in Figure 12. The temperature during the cure is taken at 2 points of interest in the laminate. The red dots denote the temperature developing over time in the area directly above the heating elements, called *P2*. The blue curve is the temperature above the junction, denoted *P1*. In stage 1, the laminate is not heated; thus, all the regions remain uncured and at the same temperature. As the heating elements are turned on and heat the laminate, one arrives at stage 2. In stage 2, the outer regions have cured enough to allow the resin to transfer loads, expand, and compress the less cured, and therefore more compliant, middle region. This effect intensifies as time and temperature progresses, as shown in stage 3.

Figure 12: The stage-wise process behind the phenomena of cure-induced wrinkles.

In stage 3, the fibres start to buckle as the two outer regions have now expanded to a much higher degree than $P1$, and this region is still softer. This effect is enhanced by the extensive geometry with such a vast length that it cannot expand at the ends far away from the cropped regions investigated. This intensifies the expansion into the softer middle region, allowing the fibres to buckle. As the curing continues, stage 4 is reached. Here, the delayed middle region has caught up in temperature and degree of cure, and thus, the whole laminate has built up its mechanical properties. The fully built-up resin stiffness will lock the buckled fibres in place, so a wrinkle will remain after the laminate has cooled down to room temperature. These aspects govern the phenomenon of wrinkles that appear in the curing process.

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Data Availability

The UMAT subroutine used for modelling is available through [23]. Additional data can be made available on request.

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